

KIOS CoE – Sandboxing use-case 3 (SUC3) - Differential Protection

1.1 Description

Differential protection is a crucial scheme that is usually used to protect power transformers, generators, and busbars from internal faults, ensuring reliability and stability in power systems through the promptly suppression of the fault. This protection scheme operates by comparing the currents entering and leaving the transformer. It is essentially based on the Kirchhoff's current law which states that the sum of the currents entering and leaving a node must be zero.

Figure 1: Testbed for differential protection of transformer.

In the framework of the SUC3 a differential protection scheme of a transformer is considered as it is shown in Figure 1. In this case, the transformer amplifies the voltage level from the medium to high voltage and is a part of the IEEE-9bus digital twin power system that is implemented in OPAL-RT. The transformer is protected by a differential protection scheme, which essentially compares the currents entering and leaving the transformer. Although, this protection scheme is state of the art equipment, the IEC 61850 standard and particularly the Sample Value (SV) protocol, modernizes this protection scheme by integrating the digital communication during the differential protection procedure of the transformer. Actually, the IEC 61850 is a global standard for communication networks and systems in substations, enabling interoperability and standardized communication among Intelligent Electronic Devices. Key components of IEC 61850 include the Generic Object-Oriented Substation Event (GOOSE) for high-speed (see SUC4 of this deliverable), event-driven messaging, the MMS for client-server communications, and the Sampled Values (SV) protocol for streaming measurement data.

The SV protocol is used to transmit sampled measurement data, such as currents and voltages, from merging units (MUs) to protection relays and other IEDs. SV protocol allows continuous and synchronized sampling of electrical signals, transmitting data over Ethernet in a digital format. This ensures high precision and low latency, which are critical for protection schemes. In this SUCs it is assumed that MUs sample the current signal at high rate (4 kHz), and the SVs from the sinusoidal current signal is sent to through the IEC 61850 SV protocol. Without loss of generality the MUs are emulated to the digital twin environment.

According to Figure 1, the SVs are transferred to the differential protection scheme that its logic was implemented to the Typhoon controller. The Typhoon controller receives the SV streams corresponding to the primary and secondary currents of the transformer and calculates the differential current by subtracting the secondary current from the primary current. The differential current is then compared against a threshold. If the differential current exceeds the threshold, an internal fault is indicated, and the protection relay issues a trip command to isolate the transformer. The trip commands that are issued by the differential protection scheme of this SUC are sent back to the digital twin environment and in particular to the breakers of the transformer to open.

Differential protection scheme in transformer is vital for the protection of the transformer and the suppress of the fault before expanding to a larger part of the system. It has however, detrimental effects when such a scheme is compromised by an attacker. In this SUC it is assumed that MITM attack occur during the SVs transfer from the field to the differential protection. The attacker aims to have the transformer out of the operation by deceiving the differential protection through FDI in order to trip the breakers of the transformer. Such attack can affect directly the energy supply of the customers at the MV and LV levels. The attack scenario for this SUC is described in Section 1.2, while the results from the execution of the MITM attacks are discussed in Section 1.3.

1.2 Attack scenarios

The attacks investigated in this SUC are summarized in Table 1. In summary, the attack scenarios deal with MITM attack that target the fault data injection to the IEC 61850 SVs.

Table 1: Attack Vector for SUC3

Attack Vector	Description
Attacked devices	Differential protection relay
Protocols	IEC 61850 Sample value
Type of attack	1. MITM with FDI
Attack vector	Attacker should have access to local network
Complexity	1. MITM and FDI: High complexity with precise value change of the current measurements in order to deceive the wide area protection scheme for the occurrence of a fault.
Privillages required	The attack is launched virtually within the digital twin without requiring any privileges (e.g., administration rights) to access the device.
User interaction	None - There is no requirement for the attacker to authenticate to launch the attack.

1.3 Analysis of results

In this section two selected scenarios (S1-S2) associated to SUC3 are presented and analyzed. The first scenario (S1) deals with the occurrence of a fault on the high voltage side of a transformer, which protected by a differential protection scheme. This scenario aims to showcase the expected operation of the differential protection scheme during a fault in the transformer. The second scenario (S2) examines the launch of a cyber-attack on the IEC 61850 SV protocol which essentially alters the SVs that are used in the differential protection relay. Specifically, this scenario examines a MITM attack with FDI on SV measurements that are captured from the high voltage side of the transformer. An impact assessment is performed for each scenario to demonstrate how the cyberattacks can affect the operation of the power system. The following subsections include illustrative plots showing the results obtained for each scenario of the SUC3 while a discussion regarding the impact of the cyberattack in the power system is also included.

1.3.1 SUC3/S1 – Differential protection operation during transformer fault

The first scenario (S1) of SUC3 focuses on a fault occurred at transformer’s HV side of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system. Specifically, in this scenario, a short-circuit fault occurred in the range of HV/MV transformer of the system, causing a significant increase on the current flow at its HV side, as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Normal operation where the protection is able to clear the fault occurred on HV side of the transformer (sinusoidal format)

During normal operating conditions (before 5.8 seconds and after 22.5 seconds), the power system provides uninterrupted supply in the system through the HV/MV transformer with the current at the HV side to reach 324 A and in the MV side 6750 A.

In this scenario, a short-circuit fault occurred at 5.8 seconds and lasts 5 seconds, leading to the increase of current flow in the HV side of HV/MV transformer up to 737 A, as shown in Figure 3 (b). Consequently, the overall operation of the system is impacted. Since the transformer is protected by a differential protection scheme, after the occurrence of the fault the protection is activated and trips the transformer breakers. Therefore, the current flow through the transformer is interrupted in both sides of the transformer (as illustrated in Figure 3). With the fault clearance, the breakers of the line reclose and the transformer reverts to the normal condition.

The impact assessment for the first scenario of SUC3 specify that a short-circuit fault in the range of HV/MV transformer can cause a significant increase in current flow of the transformer. The fault successfully cleared by the protection scheme, securing the system from severe power disturbances that might lead to instability issues and power infrastructure damage.

1.3.2 SUC3/S2 - MITM with FDI cyber-attack in the SVs of HV transformer side

The second scenario analyses the operation of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system when a MITM and FDI attack is launched on IEC 61850 SV protocol targeting the value change of the SV measurements captured from the transformer's HV side. This specific FDI attack, (virtually implemented within the sandboxing) is characterized by high complexity, adding a multiplicative change to the current measurements before they are received by the differential protection scheme (implemented in the Typhoon controller). As a result of this attack the operation of the transformer

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Normal operation where the protection is able to clear the fault occurred on HV side of the transformer

is interrupted unexpectedly, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Attacked scenario (MITM with FDI) causing undesired relay tripping and regional blackout (sinusoidal form).

During normal operation (before 12.5 seconds), the HV/MV transformer of the system provides uninterrupted power supply by transforming the HV current (324 A) to MV current (6750 A). A MITM with FDI cyber-attack is initiated at 12.5 seconds, increasing maliciously through a multiplicative change (x1.25) the HV side current measurements of phase A (shown in Figure 5) of the transformer. These altered measurements have a significant impact on the response of the differential protection scheme since the attacker mimics a fault in the range of the transformer. Therefore, the protection scheme is activated, and the transformer is disconnected from the system as illustrated in Figure 5. Essentially, the attacker succeeds to interrupt the current that flows through the HV to MV side of the transformer causing a power deficiency in the system.

Assessing the impact of the second scenario of SUC3, it can be concluded that a MITM attack combined with FDI in the SV measurements used in the differential protection relay of the transformer significantly disrupts the normal operation of the entire system. This attack can cause unwanted power supply interruptions for end users, and the disconnection of the transformer can lead to system reconfiguration, which ultimately affects the reliability of monitoring applications in the control centre.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Attacked scenario (MITM with FDI) causing undesired relay tripping and regional blackout.

1.4 Datasets

Two main scenarios (S1-S2) associated to the operation of SUC3 are illustrated in Section 1.3. These scenarios analyse the operation of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system and the differential protection scheme under healthy conditions, cyber-attack on communication channels of IEC 61850 SVs protocol, and a fault in HV side of a transformer in the power system. The scenarios are presented with selected time-series plots in Section 1.3, accompanied a detailed analysis of the processes included and an impact assessment.

During execution of each scenario, data such as electrical measurements were captured and are collected in this section. The datasets from each SUC3 scenario are openly available and can be accessed through Zenodo repository.

As regards the datasets for the two scenarios (S1-S2) of SUC3, additional details are provided in Table 2 - Table 3, respectively.

Table 2: SUC3/S1 datasets

SUC3/S1	Differential protection operation during transformer fault
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Dataset description	<p>This dataset is related to the operation of the third sandboxing use case (SUC3) of the KIOS CoE Sandboxing for cyber-physical analysis of EPES, which examines the operation of differential protection scheme (implemented in Typhoon controller) for a HV/MV transformer. The protection scheme receives data sent through IEC 61850 SVs from the two sides of the transformer. Specifically, this dataset corresponds to the first scenario (S1) of SUC3, where a short-circuit occurred on the HV side of a HV/MV transformer of the system. More details about the scenario related to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.1 of this document.</p> <p>This dataset includes electrical measurements of the current flow, in RMS and sinusoidal format, from the HV and MV sides of HV/MV transformer of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV files which were recorded with a 30-second and 40-second time resolution, respectively. The measurements of RMS values were recorded by the Typhoon controller, while the sinusoidal measurements were recorder by OPAL-RT.</p>
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse the operation of protection scheme during normal conditions and under short-circuit fault. Impact assessment of faults occurred in power systems. Test and evaluate protection scheme to prevent the fault spread to the rest of the power system.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Electron_SUC3_S1_DifferentialProtection_Transformer_RMS.mat] [Electron_SUC3_S1_DifferentialProtection_TransformerSineWave.mat] [Electron_SUC3_S1_DifferentialProtection_Transformer_RMS.csv]
File size	32 MB, 15 MB, 508 MB
Data collection	The dataset for RMS values was collected through the Typhoon controller which is connected in the loop with the power system digital twin running in the real time simulator. Regarding the sine wave values, the dataset was collected through OPAL-RT (in the real time simulation environment), where the power system digital twin runs.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current flow (in A) from HV and MV sides of HV/MV transformer of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system
Metadata and keywords	Power system, sampled values, differential protection, short-circuit fault, electrical measurements.

Table 3: SUC3/S2 datasets

SUC3/S2	MITM with FDI cyber-attack in the SVs of HV transformer side
Dataset description	<p>This dataset is associated to the operation of the third sandboxing use case (SUC3) described in this supporting document. This use case investigates the operation of differential protection scheme for a HV/MV transformer through Typhoon controller which receives data sent through IEC 61850 SVs. More specific, this dataset corresponds to the second scenario (S2) of SUC3, where a MITM with FDI cyber-attack is conducted on the measurements of the HV side of the transformer, virtually implemented within the sandboxing, and introduces a multiplicative change to the current measurements before they are received by the differential protection scheme via IEC 61850 protocol. Section 1.3.1 of this supporting document provided more details about the scenario related to this dataset.</p> <p>This dataset includes electrical measurements of the current flow, in RMS and sinusoidal format, from the HV and MV sides of HV/MV transformer of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV files which were recorded with a 30-second and 40-second time resolution, respectively. The measurements of RMS values were recorded by the Typhoon controller, while the measurements from the sine waves were recorder by OPAL-RT.</p>
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse the operation of protection scheme during healthy communication and under MITM and FDI attack. Impact assessment of cyber-attacks in such smart grid applications.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test and evaluate cyber-security solutions to prevent the impact on power infrastructure.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Electron_SUC3_S2_MITM_FDI_IEC61850_SV_RMS.mat] • [Electron_SUC3_S2_MITM_FDI_IEC61850_SV_SineWave.mat] • [Electron_SUC3_S2_MITM_FDI_IEC61850_SV_RMS.csv]
File size	32 MB, 15 MB, 463 MB
Data collection	The dataset for RMS values was collected through the Typhoon controller which is connected in the loop with the power system digital twin running in the real time simulator. Regarding the sine wave values, the dataset was collected through OPAL-RT (in the real time simulation environment), where the power system digital twin runs.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current flow (in A) from HV and MV sides of HV/MV transformer of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system.
Metadata and keywords	Power system, sampled values, differential protection, cyber-attacks, man-in-the-middle, false data injection, electrical measurements.